

CLASSIFICATION OF TRAFFIC SIMULATION METHODS

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Effective management of traffic flows is carried out through a control system, which is a complex of integrated tools for solving all types of transport problems based on high technologies, methods for modeling transport processes, software, organizing information flows in real time.

Modeling various processes and systems solves various problems without resorting to experiments with a real system. With the help of traffic flow modeling, you can solve problems related to the design of road networks, the preparation of transport routes and schedules for public transport, as well as optimize traffic in existing transport networks. There are a large number of modeling methods with which engineers can solve their problems. To simplify the choice of modeling method, they are classified. This helps to quickly determine which modeling method is appropriate for the problem being solved based on available data, time, computational and labor resources, as well as taking into account the required accuracy and ultimate goals of modeling. Examples of macroscopic models known as hydrodynamic models are the Lighthill-Whitham model, the Greenshields model, and the system dynamics model. Macroscopic models are built "top down" - global parameters of interaction and behavior are set for modeling.

Specialists are increasingly resorting to classifications that are based not on one attribute, but on a combination of them. One of these is the classification shown in Figure 1 according to two main features: the level of detail and the modeling method.

Fig.1-Classification of traffic flow modeling methods

The macroscopic level of detail considers traffic flow. With this simulation, you can study the average flow characteristics. For example, density, average speed, intensity, but

vehicles are not considered as separate units. Such models can be continuous, described by partial differential equations, or discrete. The Lighthill-Whitham-Richards (LWR) model reflects the main characteristics of the macroscopic approach. This model belongs to analogue models, based on the equations of hydrodynamics and the fulfillment of the law of conservation of mass. Macroscopic models are usually used to determine the travel time, average speed, network load level, traffic intensity. However, the results obtained are static and not accurate enough.

Mesomodeling describes vehicles quite accurately, but considers their behavior and interaction in the same way as at the macro level. The gravity model displays the interaction of several areas that generate traffic flows (correspondence). It is based on the law of universal gravitation. The main advantage of these models is compactness. However, these models cover only a limited set of parameters, poorly take into account the dynamics of the traffic flow.

Each machine is examined in detail in microscopic models. Micromodels gained popularity after the advent of powerful computing computers, since a large number of calculations are required. This theory is developed and subject to changes, in particular, reaction time, stability, movement are taken into account. The models describe the dynamics of an individual vehicle, which allows them to be classified as mesoscopic models. A more suitable apparatus for implementing microscopic models are cellular automata. In such models, the road is divided into cells, time is considered discrete. Each cell can have a state, which is determined by a set of rules that depend on the state of neighboring cells.

Rice. 2-The results of the model on cellular automata, to calculate the delay of cars at

different phases of the traffic light

Such a model is the best choice of traffic flows, since it can be used to model the behavior of vehicles at a regulated intersection with a high degree of detail and work out an optimization method. The advantage of such a model is its high efficiency in computer simulation.

Conclusion

The main advantage of microscopic models is the ability to obtain estimates with high accuracy. However, it takes a lot of resources to collect the initial data, it is necessary to calibrate the parameters, and high sensitivity to errors in the initial data. As a rule, the results of the work of microscopic models are such data as the length of the queue, the delay time of vehicles, the average speed, maximum or minimum speed, the time of movement of cars. For the development of modeling methods and successful implementation in the field of traffic flow management, it is necessary to develop the level of legal and organizational support, equipping with modern technical means, increasing the level of operational management and economic base.

References

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